

Practicing Serendipity: Information Encountering with Personal Productivity Apps

Sunoo, Jennifer Yoon

Simmons University, USA | jennifer.sunoo@simmons.edu

Agarwal, Naresh Kumar

Simmons University, USA | naresh.agarwal@simmons.edu

Erdelez, Sanda

Simmons University, USA | sanda.erdelez@simmons.edu

ABSTRACT

Serendipity, also known as information encountering (IE) in human information behavior, is the unexpected discovery of information that has drawn much interest from the scientific community and popular culture. Personal productivity apps typically offer services like task management and focus maintenance which are not seen as compatible with IE. This study explores if IE is present in features of personal productivity apps. Forty-four popular personal productivity apps were examined for the presence of IE features. A text analysis was also conducted to determine if IE steps were mentioned on these companies' websites. The results showed that 65.9% of the apps offered IE features. Additionally, 34.1% of the web-sites included names of IE steps. This implies that personal productivity apps are offering IE features and their websites are mentioning IE steps. This is evidence that IE features have a presence in the world of personal productivity.

KEYWORDS

Information Encountering, Serendipity, Personal Productivity App

INTRODUCTION

Many individuals seek to achieve personal productivity in their work or personal lives. It has been at the forefront of popular culture since Benjamin Franklin invented the first documented to-do list in the late 18th century (Zantal-Wiener, 2022). For many personal productivity seekers, personal productivity apps are the key to achieving their goals. Many personal productivity apps are known for supporting traditional productivity activities including focus and distraction blocking. This qualitative study examined the presence of features that support information encountering among popular personal productivity apps.

The research questions for this study were:

RQ1: What information encountering steps are supported by features of popular personal productivity apps?

RQ2: What refined information encountering steps are mentioned on personal productivity apps' websites?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information Encountering

According to Erdelez (1999), "information encountering [or serendipity] occurs when one is looking for information related to one topic and finds information related to another one" (Erdelez, 1999). The original model includes the following five steps: noticing, stopping, examining, capturing, and returning.

According to Erdelez and Makri (2020), "[s]erendipity in the context of information acquisition has also emerged as a highly important area in the field of library and information science." This led to the development of a broadened definition of Information Encountering by Erdelez and Makri (2020) to "finding interesting, useful, or potentially useful information when looking for some other information, not looking for any information in particular, or not looking for information at all" (Erdelez and Makri, 2020). There was also the development of a refined model to accompany this definition. The seven steps of this refined model are: noticing, stopping or suspending, acquiring, examining, exploring (followup seeking), capturing and storing, using and sharing.

Personal Productivity Apps

According to Leshed (2012), "productivity tools play additional roles in everyday experiences beyond simply offering efficient ways for organizing activities, events, and tasks". These roles include negotiating life goals, managing everyday priorities, socially committing to group activities, and tracing their own activities, tasks, and schedules. Leshad (2012) also went on to say that "despite living in a culture that values systematic efficiency and productivity, [study] ... interviewees described many cases in which being rational is impossible or unwanted because [r]eal life is full of dynamic, unplanned, unexpected interactions and situations".

METHODOLOGY

In the productivity app identification process, a google search was conducted using the phrase "productivity tools." This search yielded many pages of personal productivity tool app lists. Three lists of 2021 top productivity apps were selected due to their reputation: Good Housekeeping, PCMag, and TechRadar. There were 44 unique productivity apps included on these three lists. Five of the apps (Asana, Evernote, Google Suite, Microsoft Office, Todoist) were listed on two of the lists and one app (Trello) was listed on all three lists.

An initial analysis was performed to identify the presence of features in the personal productivity apps that supported information encountering. The content on the homepage and features page (if there was one) for each productivity app were visually scanned for information on features that supported any of the five steps in the original information encountering model (noticing, stopping, examining, capturing, returning).

The second analysis was a text analysis conducted by the same researcher to identify the presence on the personal productivity website homepages and features page (if there was one) of the verbs related to the refined information encountering steps (noticing, stopping or suspending, acquiring, examining, exploring (followup seeking), capturing and storing, using, sharing). The homepage and features page (if it existed) were converted into PDFs then each individually uploaded into QDA Miner Lite.

Although the initial analysis was conducted using the IE steps from the original IE model, the second analysis was conducted using the steps of the refined IE model, which the researcher viewed as more comprehensive a list of IE related verbs. The text retrieval feature was used to identify the occurrence of the verbs (notice, stop, suspend, acquire, examine, explore, followup, capture, store, use, share).

RESULTS

Initial Analysis

In response to RQ1, it was discovered that of the 44 apps identified, 29 apps (65.9%) supported at least 1 IE step. 2 apps (Evernote and Pocket) supported 5 steps, 2 apps (Apple Shortcuts and SwiftKey Keyboard) supported 4 steps, 3 apps (Dragon NaturallySpeaking, Rev, and Zapier) supported 3 steps, and 22 apps supported 1 step. Additionally, 24 apps supported noticing, 6 apps encouraged stopping, 5 apps supported examining, 6 apps supported capturing, and 7 apps supported returning. There were also 22 apps that supported 1 step, 3 apps that supported a combination of 3 steps, 2 apps that supported a combination of 4 steps, and 2 apps that supported a combination of 5 steps.

Text Analysis

In response to RQ2, a total of 15 (34.1%) of the 44 productivity apps mentioned the verbs that are part of the refined information encountering process on their homepage or features page. Six of the apps (13.6%) supported 2 steps (ABBYY FineReader, Asana, Due, Evernote, LastPass, and Todoist). Nine of the apps supported 1 step (Any.do, Basecamp, Freedom, Lucidchart, Metactrl Sync, Podio, Prezi, Swiftkey Keyboard). Thirteen productivity apps marketed themselves on their website as having a “share” feature. Thirteen productivity apps marketed themselves on their website as having a “share” feature. Five of the apps (ABBYY FineReader, Asana, Evernote, SwiftKey Keyboard, Todoist) marketed themselves on their websites as having a “capture” feature. Three productivity apps (Basecamp, Due, LastPass) marketed themselves on their websites as having a “store” feature. Eight apps mentioned the capturing or storing step (capture - 5, store - 3) and 13 apps mentioned the using and sharing step. There were also 8 apps that mentioned 1 step, and six apps that mentioned a combination of 2 steps.

ANALYSIS

The results of the initial analysis and final text analysis of the websites of the top productivity apps signify that there are information encountering steps being supported by top productivity apps. Not only do these functions exist, but the companies are marketing themselves as having these features. The more commonly mentioned steps were sharing, followed by capturing, followed by storing.

CONCLUSION

This exploration of productivity apps and IE has resulted in the conclusion that there is room for information encountering in the world of personal productivity. We live in world full of regular interruptions and these findings lead the researchers to believe that individuals are likely to get a benefit from actively engaging in IE to manage these interruptions in their lives.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you to the researchers’ families for their endless patience and moral support.

REFERENCES

- D’Alessio, F. (2020). The 3 Pillars of Productivity Tools Have Changed. Keep Productive. Retrieved from (<https://medium.com/keep-productive/the-3-pillars-of-productivity-tools-have-changed-4ee8df87d4df>).
- Erdelez, S. (1999). Information encountering: It’s more than just bumping into information. *Bulletin of the American Society for Information Science*, 25(3), 26–29.
- Erdelez, S., Makri, S. (2020). Information encountering re-encountered: A conceptual re-examination of serendipity in the context of information acquisition. *Journal of Documentation*, 76(3), 731–751.
- Free Qualitative Data Analysis Software | QDA Miner Lite. Provalis Research (2022). Retrieved from (<https://provalisresearch.com/products/qualitative-data-analysis-software/freeware/>).

- Kim, Y.-H., Choe, E. K., Lee, B., Seo, J. (2019). Understanding Personal Productivity: How Knowledge Workers Define, Evaluate, and Reflect on Their Productivity. *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–12.
- Leshed, G.: Slowing down with personal productivity tools. *Interactions: New Visions of Human-Computer Interaction*, 19(1), 58–63. (2012). doi:10.1145/2065327.2065339
- White, G., Liang, Z., & Clarke, S. (2019). A Quantified-Self Framework for Exploring and Enhancing Personal Productivity. *2019 International Conference on Content-Based Multimedia Indexing (CBMI)*, 1–6.
- Zantal-Wiener, A. (2022) A Brief History of Productivity: How Getting Stuff Done Became an Industry. Retrieved from (<https://blog.hubspot.com/marketing/a-brief-history-of-productivity>).